

Novel Silk Fibroin based Bilayer Scaffolds for Bioabsorbable Internal Biliary Stenting

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Abstract

Biliary duct reconstruction is one of the most challenging parts of liver transplantation and accounts for 40 – 60 % of complications. While current stent-based devices on the market show promising results in reducing complications, they are manufactured from permanent synthetic materials and require a second reintervention for their removal. This exposes the patients to other potential complications and increases healthcare costs. This study develops a fabrication technique to produce a bioabsorbable biliary stent based on silk fibroin. The process used a dip-coating procedure for silk fibroin that produced highly smooth monolayer tubular specimens without the use of any additional surfactants during removal. This process was combined with an electrospinning step to produce bilayer structures through the deposition of electrospun silk fibroin on the outer surface. The structures proved to have promising mechanical, morphological, and cytocompatibility properties for the use in the field of biliary stenting. Furthermore, the technique investigated proved to be reproducible, achieving an important requirement for large-scale use even in presence of a biomaterial derived from a natural source. These results show the possibility of obtaining a completely bioabsorbable internal biliary stent that does not require any second reintervention. This study can be the starting point for further investigations both in vitro and in vivo to assess the suitability of silk fibroin biliary stents for clinical applications.

Keywords

Silk fibroin, PureSilk, biliary stent, bioabsorbable, implant

1. Introduction

The common bile duct is the part of the biliary system that transports the bile stored in the gallbladder to the duodenum. It has a typical length between 75 and 110 mm and a diameter ranging from 6 to 8 mm [1]. Reconstruction of the common bile duct is an essential step during liver transplantation, a surgery that has seen a 45.6 % increase in the past ten years in the United States [2]. During liver transplantation, biliary reconstruction is typically performed through an end-to-end choledoco-choledocostomy by a duct-to-duct anastomosis between the recipient and donor tissues (see Figure 1 A). However, biliary reconstruction is considered one of the most problematic aspects of liver transplant [3] and accounts for 40 – 60 % of all complications encountered during transplantation surgery [4], with bile leaks occurring in 5.1 - 23.4 % of the cases and strictures occurring in 6.5 - 21.5 % [5]. Biliary complications can become progressively worse and lead to cholestasis, bridging fibrosis, secondary biliary cirrhosis, and graft failure [5]. These complications are ultimately associated with a high morbidity and even increased mortality [4,6–14], if not treated in a timely manner.

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Abbreviations: LD linear density, BP burst pressure, SRS suture retention strength, DC dip-coated monolayer sample, DC+ES dip-coated and electrospun bilayer sample, WVA water vapor annealing.

To prevent and effectively manage biliary complications, stenting of the biliary anastomosis has been proposed. The procedure consists of the intraoperative insertion of a tubular structure either externally through anastomosis (external stenting) or internally in the bile duct (internal stenting) to mechanically stabilize the connection and reinforce the biliary wall to prevent the formation of leakages and strictures [4]. However, these procedures have had contradictory results [3,6]. Early approaches used intraoperative external stents with T-tubes to reduce the pressure in the biliary system [3,8,10,13,14]. Nonetheless, this approach is no longer widely used due to its limited efficacy and relatively high rates of early biliary complications [7]. While early studies that used infant-feeding catheters as internal stents [10] also showed limited benefits in liver transplant surgery, more recent approaches that have designed internal stents specifically for biliary applications have been more successful. These devices [9,12] (Figure 1 B) have generally consisted of tubular structures fabricated with polyethylene, ethyl vinyl acetate, or expanded polytetrafluoroethylene (ePTFE), with ePTFE being among the most promising materials used in the gastrointestinal field [15]. The morphological surface properties of these devices also play an important role in the final outcomes, with a smooth inner surface being necessary to prevent sludge formation [1], while a higher outer surface roughness is necessary to favour epithelialisation [16] and prevent stent migration which affects 5 – 43 % of patients with internal biliary stenting [3]. While these internal stents had fewer complications compared to T-tubes [7], these devices only remain in the implanted site for a temporary period and require a second reintervention surgery to be removed [8], which leads to additional costs and further potential complications due to the surgical intervention [8].

Bioabsorbable internal stents could therefore constitute an advantageous option, despite still being in the early stages of clinical adoption [1]. While the axial and tensile properties of biliary stents dictate stent performance, in terms of migration, kinking, and sludge formation [1,17], it has been established that the functional mechanical performance of a biliary stent is only required for 8 weeks post-intervention to allow healing of the anastomosis [1]. Beyond that, overall degradation of the bioresorbable devices can take place at 6-8 months [1], since most biliary strictures tend to occur during the early implantation period (5-8 months) and on average 70 % - 87 % happen within the first year post-surgery [18]. Girard et al. [8,12] presented one of the first examples of a biodegradable internal biliary stent using a composite polymer device made of PEG-PCL-PLA (polyethylene glycol – polycaprolactone – polylactic acid). The material was used to achieve an elastic modulus similar to the physiological tissue while maintaining biodegradability. The devices were fabricated by rolling a membrane manufactured in the same material followed by a gluing procedure that consists of a partial dissolution of the polymer film edges. While this device showed its potential efficacy (even in human post-mortem conditions), it was found that the degradation time was shorter than the desired 6-month period, which meant that the device could be prone to bile leaks or to duct strictures [12]. Furthermore, all the bioabsorbable materials used present challenges caused by their synthetic origin related mainly to immunogenicity [19], infection risk, and foreign body response [20].

Figure 1 – (A) graphic representation of the bile duct anastomosis during liver transplant, (B) representation of the procedure of intraoperative stenting during liver transplant, adapted from Tashiro et al. [9].

Despite the advancements in the field of biliary stenting, technical issues relating to material and device performance are still encountered [12] and new solutions are needed. Silk fibroin is one of the two proteins that

form silk structure, it is biocompatible and bioabsorbable [21–35] and it has gained increasing interest in the biomedical field for various applications such as tissue engineering [36], eye devices [37], 3D printed bioelectronics [38], wound healing [39], drug delivery [40] and vascular grafts [41–43]. Furthermore, being the component responsible for the strength of silk fibres, it possesses great mechanical properties [44] that could be promising for internal biliary stenting. Silk fibroin also undergoes enzymatic degradation, whereby the protein is broken down into amino acids [45,46], avoiding the accumulation or production of harmful residues that can be encountered in synthetic polymers. Furthermore, silk fibroin has good processability, which means that the production of bilayer structures has been demonstrated in other applications, which could be favourable to optimise the performance of the inner and outer surfaces, to prevent sludge formation internally [1] and encourage epithelialisation externally [16]. The processability of silk fibroin to obtain different structures is particularly favourable to obtain monomaterial medical devices, which are preferred for clinical applications and correspond indeed to the FDA-approved silk fibroin-based devices (SERI Surgical Scaffold[®], DermaSilk[®], Epifibroin 0039[™]) [47,48]. An example of a bilayer silk fibroin-based structure has been reported for vascular grafts [49], whereby the combination of a lyophilized and an electrospun layer was investigated. However, both of these layers have some inherent levels of porosity, which could result in leaks. On the other hand, dip-coating, the formation of a layer of the desired material on a mandrel by immersion and withdrawal from the solution of interest, permits solid and compact tubular structures [50–53] to be achieved. However, processing silk fibroin through this approach presents certain challenges, in particular when removing from the substrate. While this problem has been solved with the use of surfactants during removal [50], this method can affect the properties of silk fibroin and leave residues on the implant surface. Despite these technical challenges, there is significant potential to develop optimised bilayer biliary stents using silk fibroin.

In the current study, a novel bioabsorbable internal bilayer biliary stent is developed using silk fibroin by combining a dip-coated inner layer and an electrospun outer layer, without the use of any additional surfactants during removal. To check an important requirement for production, the reproducibility of the technique is verified, and the resulting stents are characterised in terms of morphology and mechanical properties comparing the final devices both with a silk fibroin dip-coated only stent (monolayer) and to literature.

2. Materials and Methods

To process silk fibroin, the silk protein needs to be extracted from the silk *B. mori* cocoons. For this, silk fibroin aqueous solution was obtained using PureSilk[®] technology (Fibrothelium GmbH, Aachen, Germany), enabling medical-grade quality production of silk on an industrial scale for a broad range of concentrations. Briefly, fibroin was separated from sericin by degumming it in a hot alkali solution before dissolving it in a proprietary non-toxic solvent system based on Ajisawa's reagent. The dissolved silk fibroin was fully dialysed against VE water within 8 hours using tailored extraction processing. The fibroin concentration used in this study was adjusted to 20 wt% and stored at 4°C. The fibroin was then processed to obtain a bilayer structure exploiting the easy processability of silk fibroin.

2.1 Production

The entire production process is shown in Figure 2. Teflon mandrels with a length of 120 mm and a diameter of 3 mm (Goodfellow Cambridge Ltd., Huntingdon, UK) and 4 mm (Dr. Dietrich Müller, Großenkneten, Germany) were selected, considering that internal biliary stents had a median size of 3.33 mm, with a range between 2.67 mm and 4 mm [3]. Two types of samples were produced whereby (i) monolayer devices were produced with dip-coating only (DC, monolayer) and (ii) bilayer devices were produced using a combined dip-coating and electrospinning (DC+ES, bilayer) process. Before use, all the mandrels were rinsed with ethanol and water to ensure the absence of particles possibly affecting the fabrication procedure.

2.1.1 Monolayer Production

The first step consisted of the fabrication of the inner structure by multilayer dip-coating deposition. The entire procedure was performed on a numerically controlled setup that allowed reproducibility of the process, by maintaining a constant withdrawal velocity. The setup was composed by two stepper motors (ZSS 32.200.1.2, Phythron, Gröbenzell, Germany), two linear guides (KR20, THK Co. Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) and a control unit (MCC-2, Phythron, Gröbenzell, Germany), while Mini-Log Comm (Phythron, Gröbenzell, Germany) was used as software

for programming the production routine. The immersion and withdrawal velocities were constant at 5 mm/s and the immersion time was 30 s.

The fibroin solution used for the dip-coating procedure had a 20 wt% concentration and was mixed with glycerol (VWR, Radnor, Pennsylvania, USA) in a proportion equal to the 30 % of fibroin content to induce the insolubility of silk fibroin and to improve the flexibility of the device. The dip-coating procedure was repeated 8 times with a drying process in between the layers performed at 30°C for 2 hours. The direction of coating was inverted after 4 layers to ensure a homogenous distribution of the dip-coating layer. After the last drying step, 20 mm of coating was removed from each extremity of the substrate due to the incomplete immersion given by the inversion procedure.

To remove the coating structure from the substrate, water vapor annealing was performed. Water vapor annealing consists of the exposition of the samples to water vapor to alter the crystallinity of silk fibroin [54]. The process was carried out at 25°C under vacuum [54] inside a vacuum oven (WOV-30, Witeg Labortechnik, Wertheim, Germany) for three hours. Afterwards, the coating part could be easily pulled out of the substrate obtaining the entire tubular dip-coated layer.

2.1.2 Bilayer Production

To produce the bilayer devices, the dip-coated monolayer specimens underwent an additional step, whereby an outer layer was produced through a nozzle-less electrospinning procedure performed on a custom electrospinning setup (Fibrothelium GmbH, Aachen, Germany). In brief, a rotating stainless-steel spinneret was placed inside a 21 wt% silk fibroin aqueous solution reservoir and connected to a gear motor while the dip-coated tube was placed on a rotating aluminium rod-collector (3 mm diameter, 300 mm length) at a distance of 240 mm from the tip of the spinneret. A high voltage difference of 45-55 kV was applied between the collector and the reservoir. Spinning was performed at room temperature for 30 minutes to enable a proper deposition of the electrospun layer. Since this last layer is soluble in water, the structure was crosslinked through a water vapor annealing process [55–58], whereby samples were exposed to water at 45°C for 30 minutes to ensure the formation of β -sheets in the electrospun layer.

A total of 32 samples in 4 different batches were realised with the dip-coating procedure and 16 of them (2 batches) were electrospun to allow the comparison between the monolayer and the bilayer structures.

Figure 2 - Method used for sample preparation comprising of multilayer dip-coating deposition, water vapor annealing in vacuum, removal, electrospinning, and a final crosslinking step.

2.2 Manufacturing Reproducibility Assessment

To assess the reproducibility of the stents being prepared, the linear density (LD) was measured through a non-destructive method. The linear density was calculated as the ratio between the mass of the sample and its length (Equation 1), where the mass was measured using a precision scale (ABT 320-4M, Kern, Balingen, Germany).

$$LD \left[\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{cm}} \right] = \frac{\text{weight} [\text{mg}]}{\text{length} [\text{cm}]} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

To account for the different diameters of the samples and therefore for the different lateral surface areas of the substrates, a normalised value of linear density divided by the circumference was calculated (Equation 2).

$$\text{Normalised LD} \left[\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{cm}^2} \right] = \frac{\text{weight} [\text{mg}]}{\text{length} [\text{cm}] * \pi D_{\text{substrate}} [\text{cm}]} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

The normalised linear density was therefore calculated for each batch and the differences between the batches were analysed using a one-way ANOVA test using a cut-off p-value of 0.05.

2.3 Morphology, Thickness, and Surface Characterization

The morphological properties of the biliary stents obtained were investigated with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging (XL 30, Philips, Amsterdam, Netherlands). Specifically, the cross-section and the outer surfaces were analysed for one monolayer and one bilayer sample. Before the analysis, the samples were gold-sputtered (S150A, Edwards, Feldkirchen, Germany) and particular attention was paid to the integration between the dip-coated and the electrospun layer. Surface thickness was measured for all the samples produced with a digital micrometre (Steinle 2245, Steinle Messtechnik, Weißbach, Germany) in 9 different points per sample, while the outer and inner surface roughness was measured (4 samples per group) on both the outer and the inner surface using a 3D laser scanning confocal microscope (VK-X1050, Keyence, Osaka, Japan) equipped with a laser light source of 661 nm in wavelength. For each measurement, three lines of 1250 μm in length were considered determining the final R_a as an average.

The difference between the dip-coated only and the dip-coated and electrospun samples was analysed using Student t-tests using a cut-off p-value of 0.05.

To further characterize and check the reproducibility of the electrospinning deposition, images (n=10) were taken using a 3D laser scanning confocal microscope (VK-X1050, Keyence, Osaka, Japan). The images were then analysed in ImageJ (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, Maryland, United States) using the GIFT macro, which revealed to be effective in the detection of the diameter of the fibres forming electrospun fleeces [59].

2.4 Mechanical Characterization

Mechanical testing of specimens was performed according to ISO 7198, which is used for tubular structures and grafts. Furthermore, suture retention strength, burst pressure and tensile tests were carried out. Before each test, the samples were immersed in water for 10 minutes to ensure the complete wetting of the structures.

Suture retention strength (SRS) was measured in both monolayer (n=3) and bilayer (n=3) stents by inserting 4/0 suture (SERALON[®], Serag Wiessner, Naila, Germany), positioned 2 mm from the border similar to Pensalfini et al. [60] in a specimen of dimensions 12.5 mm x 40 mm. The tubular samples were cut longitudinally to produce a planar membrane, which was inserted into a clamp so that 25 mm remained outside the clamp itself (see Figure 3 A). A pre-load of 0.05 N was set and a constant axial displacement at a rate of 50 mm/min with a uniaxial tensile test machine (Z010, ZwickRoell, Ulm, Germany) was applied until the suture was pulled out of the membrane. The maximum force was defined as the SRS value.

The burst pressure was measured in a custom-made chamber equipped with a pressure sensor (CPG1500, Wika, Klinkenberg, Germany) and a perfusion pump (Fusion_101, Chemyx Inc., Stafford, TX, USA). Monolayer and bilayer stents (n=5 per group) were cut longitudinally and samples with an area of 1 cm² were placed in the burst chamber (Figure 3 C) and exposed to an increasing pressure by pumping water to obtain a pressure increase at a rate comprised between 10 kPa/s and 70 kPa/s as indicated in the ISO standard. The entire procedure was recorded, and the burst was indicated by a sudden decrease in pressure. The maximum pressure reached was defined as the burst strength value.

The tensile properties were measured by a uniaxial tensile test. Briefly, monolayer and bilayer stents (n=3 per group) were cut longitudinally to obtain membranes of dimensions 12.5 mm x 60 mm. The samples were clamped in the uniaxial tensile test machine (Z010, ZwickRoell, Ulm, Germany) setting the gauge length to 40 mm and the displacement rate at 50 mm/min (Figure 3 B). A pre-load of 0.05 N was applied in agreement with the literature

[61]. The thickness of the samples was measured before the test. Ultimate strain, ultimate tensile strength, and elastic modulus were extracted from the test and analysed.

A qualitative bending test was performed on a dip-coated stent to ensure the usability of the device and the absence of ruptures in the layer. Briefly, a 4 mm diameter dip-coated stent was immersed in water for 10 minutes and then inserted over a Teflon mandrel with a compatible diameter. The mandrel was then bended and deformed and the appearance of the stent during the test was recorded.

A Student t-test was performed to investigate the differences between the monolayer and the bilayer stents using a cut-off value of 0.05.

Figure 3 - Setups used for the mechanical characterization: (A) suture retention strength, (B) tensile test, (C) burst pressure.

2.5 Cell Viability and Proliferation

Human skin fibroblast (HDF) cultures were established by outgrowth from skin biopsies of healthy donors in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) (Gibco, 41965) supplemented with 10 % fetal calf serum (Gibco, 10270-106), penicillin/streptomycin (100 U/ml each) (Bio-chrome, A2213), 2 mM L-Glutamine (Biochrom, K0282) and ascorbic acid (50 µg/ml). The human dermal fibroblasts were seeded with an initial density on each SF biliary stent in 24-well cell culture plates containing 200 µL of DMEM media. The stents were cut into equal pieces (0.5 cm) and sterilized by immersing them in 70 wt% ethanol then washed twice with sterile PBS. The cell-seeded biliary stents were cultivated in an incubator at 37 °C and 5 % CO₂.

Live/dead staining was performed, and cell cytotoxicity in HDFs cocultured on the SF stents (7×10^4 cells/mL) was observed on day 7. The intracellular esterase-catalysed hydrolysis of Calcein AM stained live cells in green, while propidium iodide, which bonded to nucleic acids and permeated damaged membranes, stained dead cells in red. The samples were examined under a confocal scanning microscope (Zeiss Group, Oberkochen, Germany). The cell proliferation of the HDFs co-cultured with the biliary stents was investigated with an XTT assay. Briefly, after 1, 4,

and 7 days, XTT reagents were added to the cells cocultured with silk fibroin stents and incubated for 4 hours. An indirect cytotoxicity test was also performed on day 7, with the conditional media of the biliary stents. The silk fibroin stents were incubated with media for 7 days and the conditional media was added to cells for 24 hours in relation to positive and negative control (normal DMEM media). Absorbance was measured at 450 nm with a microplate reader. The tests were performed in duplicates for biological and technical replicates. 10 % Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was used as the toxic positive control reference and plastic coverslips were used as the nontoxic negative control reference. Student t-tests were performed to investigate the differences between the samples.

3. Results

3.1 Monolayer and Bilayer Biliary Stent Production

The dip-coating process was performed successfully, and the monolayer stents that were obtained are shown in Figure 4 as “dip-coated batch”. This technique was reliably reproducible, with the shape of the mandrel and the macroscopic analysis revealing a homogeneous structure without gradients in coating distribution.

Figure 4 also shows the bilayer biliary stents that were produced through the combined dip-coated and electrospinning process. Macroscopically, these samples had a homogeneous appearance, and the two layers were well integrated, without any peeling effect evident between the dip-coated inner structure and the outer electrospun fleece. Furthermore, the electrospun outer layer was uniformly distributed across the stent structure without any gaps.

Figure 4 - Samples produced via dip-coating next to the substrates used and the same samples after electrospinning.

3.2 Manufacturing Reproducibility Assessment

The manufacturing reproducibility of both the monolayer and bilayer stents are presented in Figure 5, in terms of the normalised LD. The results show that there was no statistical difference between the LD of the batches for the monolayer samples (see Figure 5 A), with the average normalised LD for all batches being 15.10 ± 1.37 mg/cm². The normalised linear density for the two bilayer batches is also shown in Figure 5 B. Even in the presence of a second layer, the difference between the two batches remained not statistically significant with an average value of 21.27 ± 2.35 mg/cm². Thanks to the non-destructive method used, all the four batches of samples could be measured even before the electrospinning of two of them.

Figure 5 - Normalised linear density for the (A) monolayer and (B) bilayer samples. This indicator is used to verify the reproducibility of the process.

3.3 Morphological Characterization

Figure 6 D shows a representative SEM image of a monolayer specimen and demonstrates that the dip-coated layer was uniformly distributed around the circumference, with a constant thickness. On the other hand, Figure 6 E shows a representative image of the bilayer specimen, where both the dip-coated and the electrospun layers are well integrated, with no gaps or delamination detected. As regards the outer surfaces, Figure 6 F shows that the monolayer structure was extremely smooth and did not present any particular irregularity, while Figure 6 G shows that the outer surface of the bilayer dip-coated and electrospun stents were characterised by the microfibrils typical of electrospinning.

Figure 6 A shows the thickness values obtained for both the monolayer and bilayer stents. While the average thickness detected for the monolayer stents was $130 \pm 15.80 \mu\text{m}$, the average thickness of the bilayer samples was $223.68 \pm 23.69 \mu\text{m}$ highlighting a significant difference ($p\text{-value} < 0.001$). This thickness was similar to other devices from a similar application produced by Laukkarinen et al. [62] ($250 \mu\text{m}$). The thickness value could be analysed together with the normalised linear density obtaining a linear relationship with a good R^2 value as shown in Figure 6 B.

Figure 6 C shows the roughness measurements of both the monolayer and bilayer stents. Here, the roughness of the inner surface showed no statistical differences between the monolayer and bilayer stents, where monolayer samples exhibited an average roughness equal to $1.129 \pm 0.111 \mu\text{m}$ and bilayer to $1.301 \pm 0.248 \mu\text{m}$. On the other hand, the surface roughness of the outer surface of the bilayer stents was significantly higher, with the monolayer stents having an average roughness of $0.096 \pm 0.052 \mu\text{m}$ and the average for the bilayer samples was $3.829 \pm 0.808 \mu\text{m}$ ($p\text{-value} < 0.001$).

Figure 7 shows the results obtained regarding the morphological analysis of the electrospun layer. Specifically, the histogram represented in Figure 7 C shows a strong peak corresponding to a diameter of $1.442 \mu\text{m}$ proving the uniform distribution of the silk fibroin fibres. Furthermore, the reproducibility of the diameter was proved in all the 10 samples analysed (Figure 7 D).

Figure 6 - (A) investigation on the thickness of the stents with a significant difference between the monolayer (DC) and bilayer (DC+ES) samples compared to stents used in literature [62], (B) linear relationship between thickness and linear density, (C) roughness results for the monolayer (DC) and bilayer (DC+ES) samples on both inner and outer surface showing a significant difference in the results regarding the outer surface, (D) cross-section of a monolayer sample showing the uniform distribution of silk fibroin, (E) cross-section of a bilayer sample showing the integration between the dip-coated and the electrospun layer, (F) outer surface of the monolayer sample with a smooth appearance, (G) outer electrospun surface showing the presence of fibres and an increased roughness.

Figure 7 - Reproducibility of the electrospinning deposition: laser scanning microscope image of the surface of one sample (A), image after the thresholding procedure performed with the GIFT macro (B), representative histogram showing the distribution of the fibre diameters with a Gaussian fitting (C), fibre diameter detected in the 10 samples analysed (D).

3.4 Mechanical Characterization

Figure 8 A shows the SRS of the monolayer (1.11 ± 0.06 N) and bilayer (1.20 ± 0.30 N) stents, with no statistically significant differences between groups (p -value > 0.60). The average force-displacement curves shown in Figure 8 B show the similarity of these two kinds of samples in the test. Importantly, both monolayer and bilayer specimens achieved the minimal suture retention strength value necessary for vascular grafts to enter clinical trials, as outlined by Konig et al. [63].

Figure 8 C shows burst pressure values with no significant difference (p -value = 0.87) between the monolayer and the bilayer samples. These values can be analysed in relation to the average bile duct pressure reported by Pitt et al. [64], which was reported as 22 mmHg, while the maximum pressure in the common bile duct reported by Abdallah et al. [65] was 195 mmHg. The measured burst pressure of the monolayer dip-coated only samples was 651.05 ± 104.74 mmHg, while the burst pressure of the dip-coated and electrospun samples was 637.85 ± 146.64 mmHg, which are substantially higher than the maximum values reported for the bile duct. Figure 8 D and Figure 8 E show the configuration of the setup before and after the burst of the sample.

Figure 8 – (A) suture retention strength of monolayer (DC) and bilayer (DC+ES) samples compared to the threshold identified for vascular grafts to enter clinical trials [63], (B) average force-displacement curves of the suture retention strength tests showing the similarity between the samples. (C) burst pressure results of both monolayer (DC) and bilayer (DC+ES) samples compared to the bile duct average pressure [64] and to the maximum pressure in the common bile duct [65], (D) and (E) frames of the burst pressure test before and after the burst.

Figure 9 presents the tensile properties of the monolayer and bilayer stents. Representative stress-strain curves from both stents are shown in Figure 9 A, with the monolayer stents generally having a higher stress response. In particular, the elastic modulus (Figure 9 B) of the monolayer samples was 38.54 ± 5.79 MPa, while the elastic modulus of the bilayer stents was 27.44 ± 2.97 MPa. These two values showed a statistically significant difference (p -value = 0.042). There was a statistically significant difference found between the ultimate failure strain (Figure 9 C) of the monolayer and the bilayer stents (p -value = 0.12), with average values equal to 29.27 ± 3.29 % and 34.03 ± 2.28 % respectively. The ultimate tensile strength (Figure 9 D) of the monolayer stents (4.13 ± 0.32 MPa) was statistically higher than the bilayer stents (2.73 ± 0.32 MPa), with both of these values comparable to that of biological tissue samples from the oesophagus [66] and equal to 2.19 MPa.

The usability of the stents in terms of flexibility was proved also in the qualitative bending test (Figure 9 E). During the test, the samples showed no ruptures in the structure with the formation of wrinkles in correspondence of the curving segment, but without being altered in its structural integrity.

Figure 9 - (A) average stress-strain curves of the monolayer (DC) and bilayer (DC+ES) samples during the tensile test, (B) elastic modulus obtained for the samples, (C) ultimate strain obtained for the samples, (D) ultimate stress obtained for the samples compared to the oesophageal tissue [66], (E) DC stent during a qualitative bending test.

3.5 Cell Viability and Proliferation

Cell adhesion and proliferation were supported by these novel biocompatible biliary stents. As illustrated in Figure 10 A, the XTT assay showed that when the cells were co-cultured either with the stents or with the conditional media, there was no loss in cell viability as compared to the control group. The XTT assay showed a greater cell proliferation on the outer surface (ES) with respect to the inner surface (DC) after 1 day, with silk fibroin-based biliary stents exerting better proliferation than controls between 4th and 7th days without a statistically significant difference between the two surfaces. After 7 days of culture, live/dead assay showed that HDFs had good cell viability on the silk fibroin biliary stents, without resulting in cell death (Figure 10 B).

The trends observed in cell viability were further investigated using live-dead staining. Figure 10 C, D, F, and G show the individual channel images of FDA and PI on the 7th day after seeding the HDFs on the SF biliary stents. Live fibroblasts did adhere and were found to be present on the inner and the outer surface of the stents. Insignificant or no red-coloured spots in these images indicate the absence of dead cells on these silk fibroin stents. The living cell with elongated and spread morphology was most clearly visible on the silk fibroin stents used in the study.

Figure 10 - (A) Results of the direct tests on the inner surface (DC), outer surface (ES), negative control, and positive control, (B) Results of the indirect test on the monolayer DC, the bilayer DC+ES, and the negative control, dead/live cell staining on the outer surface ES (C, D, E) and inner surface DC (F, G, H).

4. Discussion

This study has developed a novel fabrication process to produce a bioabsorbable silk fibroin-based bilayer biliary stent. This process established a novel dip-coating procedure for silk fibroin that produced highly smooth monolayer tubular specimens without the use of any additional surfactants during removal. This process was combined with an electrospinning step to produce bilayer structures through the deposition of electrospun silk fibroin on the outer surface. For the first time, this fabrication approach enables a low permeability bilayer silk fibroin structure to be produced by overcoming current limitations associated with the dip-coating of silk fibroin, improving the removal and the integration between two different layers. This approach allowed to achieve bioabsorbable monomaterial biliary stent, which is an important advantage for the clinical application [47]. The resulting mechanical behaviour and morphological properties were found to be highly favourable for biliary stent applications, with a smooth inner surface favourable for preventing sludge formation [1] and a higher outer surface roughness of the electrospun layer favourable for epithelialisation [16]. Moreover, the manufacturing process developed had excellent reproducibility, as shown by both the linear density and the thickness, thus showing the homogeneous deposition of material and laying the foundations for scaling up to a larger production process.

The majority of stents that have been developed for the bile duct have been fabricated from non-degradable polymers [9,12], which presents certain complications as a second reintervention surgery is required to remove these devices [8]. While bioabsorbable stents could overcome this limitation, they are in the early stages of development and, to date, only synthetic bioabsorbable polymers have been proposed with Girard et al [8,12] producing a composite polymer device made of PEG-PCL-PLA through a combination of solvent evaporation and

injection moulding. Our study presents the first example of a biliary stent produced from a natural polymer system, with the dip-coating fabrication process enabling the production of samples that have a homogeneous structure, whose appearance is similar to what was previously reported by Girard et al. [8]. This study also presents one of the few examples of a bilayer structure, which for the first time combined two different techniques of dip-coating and electrospinning in a stand-alone silk fibroin structure. Similar silk fibroin bilayer structures have already been investigated for vascular grafts, with the aim of combining the advantages of two different techniques [49], but these approaches fabricated their inner layer through lyophilization, which resulted in an inherent porosity in the silk fibroin structure. On the other hand, the dip-coating process that we have developed allows for the formation of a compact and dense structure that should inhibit any potential bile leaks upon implantation. This process uses water vapor annealing to remove samples from the mandrel and thereby avoids the use of additional surfactants or chemicals, which could be harmful to the use of silk fibroin as an implantable material. Furthermore, the dip-coating technique proved to be reproducible (Figure 5) even in the presence of a raw material derived from a natural source, which constitutes a significant benefit for the production of the devices. Lastly, this simple technique allows for the design of specific tubular shapes that could suitably prevent migration of the biliary stents, which affects a significant number of internal biliary stents despite not usually causing significant consequences [3].

The monolayer silk fibroin samples were produced through a dip-coating process that produced dense structures through the consolidation of thin layers, resulting in favourable mechanical properties. The subsequent application of the outer layer through electrospinning resulted in a structure that was visualized under SEM imaging and showed good integration between the dip-coated and the electrospun layer. This integration allows to obtain samples that are composed of a single material thus highlighting the potential of silk fibroin in terms of processability. The differences in terms of thickness and outer surface are clearly visible under SEM and show the morphology of the additional electrospun layer. Accordingly, the differences were quantified in terms of roughness and thickness (Figure 6A-C). The thickness of the final bilayer structure seems to be promising when compared to the values reported for similar devices in the literature [62]. Furthermore, the thickness could be adjustable by varying the number of dip-coating layers or the duration of the electrospinning procedure matching different needs. Indeed, Choudhury et al. [1] reported that thin stents are more suitable for the prevention of bile leakage, while thicker and more rigid structures could be used for fibrous blockages. As shown in Figure 6 C, a linear relationship between the normalised linear density and the thickness was determined. This characteristic is particularly useful in the light of a potential large-scale production of such stents because it would permit to predict an important property such as thickness with a non-destructive method. With regard to roughness, there was a clear difference between the inner and the outer surface in both cases. However, while for the monolayer stents the roughness decreases going from the inner to the outer surface, in the bilayer samples the electrospinning significantly increases the outer roughness. This enables an inner roughness to be achieved that is comparable to polyurethane membranes that are currently used in the field [67] and an increased outer roughness to favour the epithelial cells proliferation on the silk fibroin stent [16]. Furthermore, smooth inner surfaces are needed in the field of internal biliary stents because this leads to less sludge accumulation [1]. The electrospinning procedure proved also to be reproducible in terms of the morphology obtained, fulfilling another important requirement for the medical device industry.

With regards to the mechanical properties, both the monolayer and bilayer stents did not show any differences in the SRS between the two groups, indicating that the dip-coated layer is largely responsible for the mechanical properties. Furthermore, dividing the SRS values by the thickness, an average value of 8.31 N/mm was obtained for DC stents and 4.72 N/mm for the DC+ES showing how the application of the electrospun layer had a significant effect in terms of morphology, but did not contribute to the mechanical properties of the stents. The value obtained for SRS is considerably lower than the value reported in the literature for non-resorbable materials such as ePTFE (3.19 ± 1.49 N) [68], but it is more than double the value reported by Konig et al. [63] for vascular grafts to enter clinical trials (0.49 N). Considering that cardiovascular devices are implanted in a high-pressure system, it could be hypothesized that the SRS value of these stents could be sufficient for the designed application. However, in vivo data are necessary to support this hypothesis. Burst pressure is another important property for stents in pressurized systems. In particular, in the case of bile ducts the presence of strictures could increase the pressure causing leakages [5]. It is therefore essential that the stents are able to withstand physiological pressures. As shown in Figure 8 C, the burst pressure measured for the stents in both cases was more than three times higher than the maximum common bile duct pressure [64,65]. This is another confirmation that the dip-

coated layer is mostly responsible for the mechanical properties. The burst pressure of the silk fibroin-based stents is however half the value reported for ePTFE (1323 ± 383 mmHg) [68]. Nevertheless, the necessity of achieving such high values is still debated as there is no clear indication. Furthermore, tensile properties are essential for the success of a stent [1]. In all the tensile properties analysed (Figure 9) the dip-coating layer is the part of the structure that offers the highest resistance. Indeed, the decrease in ultimate stress and elastic modulus that can be seen in the dip-coated and electrospun samples is devoted to the fact that electrospinning increases the thickness of the samples but does not contribute significantly to the mechanical resistance. Specifically considering the elastic modulus, the values detected for the silk fibroin stents are in the range of tens of MPa and not of hundreds of MPa which is considered favourable in Girard et al. [8]. The ultimate strain is also similar to ePTFE ($26.87 \pm 5.40\%$) [68] highlighting the similarity of fibroin to one of the most used materials in the biomedical field [15]. As regards the ultimate stress, the value measured for silk fibroin stents is comparable to the value reported for a physiological mucosa such as the oesophagus [66] and so appropriate for the use also in the biliary field.

Favourable biocompatibility is a crucial need for scaffolds in clinical applications [69]. The inner and outer surfaces of the SF biliary stents were evaluated using *in vitro* cell culture studies. *In vitro* tests conducted over a 7-day period are adequate to offer valid and sensitive information on the functioning of this material as a potential scaffold for biliary stenting. We describe in this study the *in vitro* behaviour of human dermal fibroblasts on these novel silk fibroin structures, which may be used in internal biliary stenting applications. According to our findings, the SF stents promote cell adhesion, growth, and proliferation. No significant difference was found in the study in the cell proliferation between the inner and the outer surface. Nonetheless, the electrospun layer was superior in the initial biological response due to the rougher morphology, while the dip-coated layer appeared to outperform the electrospun layer at day 4 and day 7. This aspect could be caused by the fact that the images at these time points consider also the cells around the stents and not only the cells adhering directly to the stent surface. Research is currently being conducted to determine how well these silk fibroin structures work for biliary stenting applications *in vivo*, as it is still difficult to fully understand the influence of such an environment on the degradation [1].

There are several limitations to this study. First, the degradation of compact silk fibroin structures as the dip-coating layer could be slower than the ideal 6-8 months [50] required by the specific application. For this reason, long-term *in vivo* tests are needed to evaluate this characteristic. In case of slow degradation, it would be possible to tune the number of dip-coated layers to find the correct balance between mechanical properties and degradation rate or to consider blends with other natural biopolymers such as collagen. Similarly, some effects such as migration and sludge formation, which are essential for the functionality of the stents, can only be tested in *in vivo* conditions in which the correct anatomical site is considered. Furthermore, in the cytocompatibility tests high adhesion and proliferation were also found on the inner film surface which could be in contrast with the literature [70,71]. This may be devoted by the capturing in the assays of the cells in the well and not only of the ones on the surfaces and further analysis is needed. Finally, the tests have been conducted in this preliminary study only on a small cohort of samples and the results in terms of manufacturing and mechanical reproducibility need to be confirmed on a larger scale. However, these first results are encouraging and suggest the possibility of a large-scale production of the biliary stents.

5. Conclusion

Our findings for the first time ever reveal the possibility of obtaining a silk fibroin bilayer internal biliary stent with a reproducible fabrication method combining two different layers and the corresponding advantages of both, electrospun and dip-coated devices. The mechanical properties tested showed the suitability of the material for the application considered and make silk fibroin a promising candidate in the relatively new field of bioabsorbable materials used for biliary treatments. This study can be considered an important first step to show the feasibility of both silk fibroin as an innovative biomaterial and the applied design for use in biliary stenting.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The ethical statement number is 08-144. The aim of the statement is to study the interaction of the human dermal fibroblasts with the surrounding matrix.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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References

1. Choudhury S, Asthana S, Homer-Vanniasinkam S, Chatterjee K. Emerging trends in biliary stents: a materials and manufacturing perspective. *Biomater Sci* [Internet]. 2022;10(14):3716–29. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/d2bm00234e>
2. Wang S, Toy M, Hang Pham TT, So S. Causes and trends in liver disease and hepatocellular carcinoma among men and women who received liver transplants in the U.S., 2010-2019. *PLoS One*. 2020;15(9 September):1–14.
3. Girard E, Risse O, Abba J, Medici M, Leroy V, Chirica M, et al. Internal biliary stenting in liver transplantation. *Langenbeck's Arch Surg*. 2018;403(4):487–94.
4. Koksai AS, Eminler AT, Parlak E, Gurakar A. Management of biliary anastomotic strictures after liver transplantation. *Transplant Rev* [Internet]. 2017;31(3):207–17. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.trre.2017.03.002>
5. Jung DH, Ikegami T, Balci D, Bhangui P. Biliary reconstruction and complications in living donor liver transplantation. *Int J Surg* [Internet]. 2020;82(April):138–44. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijvsu.2020.04.069>
6. Elkoms BE, Abdelaal A. Do We Need to Use a Stent in Biliary Reconstruction to Decrease the Incidence of Biliary Complications in Liver Transplantation? A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *J Gastrointest Surg*. 2023;27(1):180–96.
7. Yoon YC, Etesami K, Kaur N, Emamaullee J, Kim J, Zielsdorf S, et al. Biliary Internal Stents and Biliary Complications in Adult Liver Transplantation. *Transplant Proc* [Internet]. 2021;53(1):171–6. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2020.06.019>
8. Girard E, Chagnon G, Broisat A, Dejean S, Soubies A, Gil H, et al. From in vitro evaluation to human postmortem pre-validation of a radiopaque and resorbable internal biliary stent for liver transplantation applications. *Acta Biomater* [Internet]. 2020;106:70–81. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2020.01.043>
9. Tashiro H, Ogawa T, Itamoto T, Ushitora Y, Tanimoto Y, Oshita A, et al. Synthetic Bioabsorbable Stent Material for Duct-to-Duct Biliary Reconstruction. *J Surg Res*. 2009;151(1):85–8.
10. Ong M, Slater K, Hodgkinson P, Dunn N, Fawcett J. To stent or not to stent: the use of transanastomotic biliary stents in liver transplantation and patient outcomes. *ANZ J Surg*. 2018;88(6):603–6.
11. Janousek L, Maly S, Oliverius M, Kocik M, Kucera M, Fronek J. Bile Duct Anastomosis Supplied With Biodegradable Stent in Liver Transplantation: The Initial Experience. *Transplant Proc* [Internet]. 2016;48(10):3312–6. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2016.09.039>
12. Girard E, Chagnon G, Moreau-Gaudry A, Letoublon C, Favier D, Dejean S, et al. Evaluation of a

- biodegradable PLA–PEG–PLA internal biliary stent for liver transplantation: in vitro degradation and mechanical properties. *J Biomed Mater Res - Part B Appl Biomater*. 2021;109(3):410–9.
13. Roos FJM, Poley JW, Polak WG, Metselaar HJ. Biliary complications after liver transplantation; recent developments in etiology, diagnosis and endoscopic treatment. *Best Pract Res Clin Gastroenterol* [Internet]. 2017;31(2):227–35. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.bpg.2017.04.002>
 14. Jung SW, Kim DS, Yu YD, Suh SO. Clinical outcome of internal stent for biliary anastomosis in liver transplantation. *Transplant Proc*. 2014;46(3):856–60.
 15. Kaltsidis H, Mansoor W, Park JH, Song HY, Edwards DW, Laasch HU. Oesophageal stenting: Status Quo and future challenges. *Br J Radiol*. 2018;91(1091).
 16. Li Y, Yang Y, Yang L, Zeng Y, Gao X, Xu H. Poly(ethylene glycol)-modified silk fibroin membrane as a carrier for limbal epithelial stem cell transplantation in a rabbit LSCD model. *Stem Cell Res Ther*. 2017;8(1):1–19.
 17. Isayama H, Nakai Y, Hamada T, Matsubara S, Kogure H, Koike K. Understanding the Mechanical forces of Self-Expandable Metal Stents in the Biliary Ducts. *Curr Gastroenterol Rep* [Internet]. 2016;18(12):1–6. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11894-016-0538-5>
 18. Keane MG, Devlin J, Harrison P, Masadeh M, Arain MA, Joshi D. Diagnosis and management of benign biliary strictures post liver transplantation in adults. *Transplant Rev* [Internet]. 2021;35(1):100593. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trre.2020.100593>
 19. Zhang F, Liu MR, Wan HT. Discussion about several potential drawbacks of PEGylated therapeutic proteins. *Biol Pharm Bull*. 2014;37(3):335–9.
 20. Martins JA, Lach AA, Morris HL, Carr AJ, Mouthuy PA. Polydioxanone implants: A systematic review on safety and performance in patients. *J Biomater Appl*. 2020;34(7):902–16.
 21. Khalilpour P, Lampe K, Wagener M, Stigler B, Heiss C, Ullrich MS, et al. Ag/SiOx/Cy plasma polymer coating for antimicrobial protection of fracture fixation devices. *J Biomed Mater Res - Part B Appl Biomater*. 2010;94(1):196–202.
 22. Schmidmaier G, Wildemann B, Stemberger A, Haas NP, Raschke M. Biodegradable poly(D,L-lactide) coating of implants for continuous release of growth factors. *J Biomed Mater Res*. 2001;58(4):449–55.
 23. Wang C, Fang H, Hang C, Sun Y, Peng Z, Wei W, et al. Fabrication and characterization of silk fibroin coating on APTES pretreated Mg-Zn-Ca alloy. *Mater Sci Eng C* [Internet]. 2020 May;110(September 2018):110742. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2020.110742>
 24. Zhou W, Yan J, Li Y, Wang L, Jing L, Li M, et al. Based on the synergistic effect of Mg²⁺ and antibacterial peptides to improve the corrosion resistance, antibacterial ability and osteogenic activity of magnesium-based degradable metals. *Biomater Sci*. 2021 Feb;9(3):807–25.
 25. Juncos Bombin AD, Dunne NJ, McCarthy HO. Electrospinning of natural polymers for the production of nanofibres for wound healing applications. *Mater Sci Eng C*. 2020;114(February):110994.
 26. Jiang J, Ai C, Zhan Z, Zhang P, Wan F, Chen J, et al. Enhanced Fibroblast Cellular Ligamentization Process to Polyethylene Terephthalate Artificial Ligament by Silk Fibroin Coating. *Artif Organs*. 2016 Apr;40(4):385–93.
 27. Bitar L, Isella B, Bertella F, Bettker C, Harings J, Kopp A, et al. Sustainable Bombyx mori's silk fibroin for biomedical applications as a molecular biotechnology challenge: A Review. *Int J Biol Macromol* [Internet]. 2024;130374. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.130374>
 28. Cai J, Zhang L, Chen J, Chen S. Silk fibroin coating through EDC/NHS crosslink is an effective method to promote graft remodeling of a polyethylene terephthalate artificial ligament. *J Biomater Appl*. 2019 May;33(10):1407–14.
 29. Cai J, Wan F, Dong Q, Jiang J, Ai C, Sheng D, et al. Silk fibroin and hydroxyapatite segmented coating enhances graft ligamentization and osseointegration processes of the polyethylene terephthalate artificial ligament: In vitro and in vivo. *J Mater Chem B*. 2018 Sep;6(36):5738–49.

30. Tanaka T, Abe Y, Cheng CJ, Tanaka R, Naito A, Asakura T. Development of Small-Diameter Elastin-Silk Fibroin Vascular Grafts. *Front Bioeng Biotechnol.* 2021;8(January):1–12.
31. Ni Y, Zhao X, Zhou L, Shao Z, Yan W, Chen X, et al. Radiologic and histologic characterization of silk fibroin as scaffold coating for rabbit tracheal defect repair. *Otolaryngol - Head Neck Surg.* 2008 Aug;139(2):256–61.
32. Actis L, Gaviria L, Guda T, Ong JL. Antimicrobial surfaces for craniofacial implants: state of the art. *J Korean Assoc Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2013;39(2):43.
33. Pitarresi G, Palumbo FS, Calascibetta F, Fiorica C, Di Stefano M, Giammona G. Medicated hydrogels of hyaluronic acid derivatives for use in orthopedic field. *Int J Pharm.* 2013;449(1–2):84–94.
34. Qu Y, Hong G, Liu L, Sasaki K, Chen X. Evaluation of silk fibroin electrogel coating for zirconia material surface. *Dent Mater J.* 2019 Oct;38(5):813–20.
35. Xu W, Yagoshi K, Asakura T, Sasaki M, Niidome T. Silk Fibroin as a Coating Polymer for Sirolimus-Eluting Magnesium Alloy Stents. *ACS Appl Bio Mater.* 2020 Jan;3(1):531–8.
36. Kundu B, Rajkhowa R, Kundu SC, Wang X. Silk fibroin biomaterials for tissue regenerations. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev [Internet].* 2013;65(4):457–70. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2012.09.043>
37. Madden PW, Klyubin I, Ahearne MJ. Silk fibroin safety in the eye: A review that highlights a concern. *BMJ Open Ophthalmol.* 2020;5(1):1–10.
38. Mu X, Sahoo JK, Cebe P, Kaplan DL. Photo-crosslinked silk fibroin for 3d printing. *Polymers (Basel).* 2020;12(12):1–18.
39. Sultan T, Lee OJ, Kim SH, Ju HW, Park CH. *Silk Fibroin in Wound Healing.* 2018;
40. Ma Y, Canup BSB, Tong X, Dai F, Xiao B. Multi-Responsive Silk Fibroin-Based Nanoparticles for Drug Delivery. *Front Chem.* 2020;8(November):1–5.
41. Kiritani S, Kaneko J, Ito D, Morito M, Ishizawa T, Akamatsu N, et al. Silk fibroin vascular graft: a promising tissue-engineered scaffold material for abdominal venous system replacement. *Sci Rep [Internet].* 2020;10(1):1–9. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78020-y>
42. Asakura T, Tanaka T, Tanaka R. *Advanced Silk Fibroin Biomaterials and Application to Small- Diameter Silk Vascular Grafts.* 2019;
43. Nakazawa Y, Sato M, Takahashi R, Aytemiz D, Takabayashi C, Tamura T, et al. Development of Small-Diameter Vascular Grafts Based on Silk Fibroin Fibers from *Bombyx mori* for Vascular Regeneration. *J Biomater Sci Polym Ed.* 2011;22(1–3):195–206.
44. Chen S, Liu M, Huang H, Cheng L, Zhao HP. Mechanical properties of *Bombyx mori* silkworm silk fibre and its corresponding silk fibroin filament: A comparative study. *Mater Des.* 2019;181:1–11.
45. Lu Q, Zhang B, Li M, Zuo B, Kaplan DL, Huang Y, et al. Degradation Mechanism and Control of Silk Fibroin. *Biomacromolecules.* 2011;12(4):1080–6.
46. Li M, Li J. Biodegradation behavior of silk biomaterials. *Silk Biomater Tissue Eng Regen Med.* 2014;330–48.
47. Bucciarelli A, Motta A. Use of *Bombyx mori* silk fibroin in tissue engineering: From cocoons to medical devices, challenges, and future perspectives. *Biomater Adv [Internet].* 2022;139(February):212982. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioadv.2022.212982>
48. Holland C, Numata K, Rnjak-Kovacina J, Seib FP. The Biomedical Use of Silk: Past, Present, Future. *Adv Healthc Mater [Internet].* 2019;8(1). Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30238637/>
49. Gupta P, Lorentz KL, Haskett DG, Cunnane EM, Ramaswamy AK, Weinbaum JS, et al. Bioresorbable silk grafts for small diameter vascular tissue engineering applications: In vitro and in vivo functional analysis. *Acta Biomater.* 2020;105:146–58.
50. Lovett M, Cannizzaro C, Daheron L, Messmer B, Vunjak-Novakovic G, Kaplan DL. Silk fibroin microtubes

for blood vessel engineering. *Biomaterials*. 2007;28(35):5271–9.

51. Behr JM, Irvine SA, Thwin CS, Shah AH, Bae MCK, Zussman E, et al. Matching Static and Dynamic Compliance of Small-Diameter Arteries, with Poly(lactide-co-caprolactone) Copolymers: In Vitro and In Vivo Studies. *Macromol Biosci*. 2020;20(3):1–15.
52. Park JH, Park J, Park Y, Kang JM, Ryu DS, Kyung J, et al. Acetazolamide-eluting biodegradable tubular stent prevents pancreaticojejunal anastomotic leakage. *J Control Release [Internet]*. 2021;335(December 2020):650–9. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2021.06.010>
53. Lee JE, Park SJ, Yoon Y, Son Y, Park SH. Fabrication of 3D freeform porous tubular constructs with mechanical flexibility mimicking that of soft vascular tissue. *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater [Internet]*. 2019;91(December 2018):193–201. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2018.12.020>
54. Hu X, Shmelev K, Sun L, Gil ES, Park SH, Cebe P, et al. Regulation of silk material structure by temperature-controlled water vapor annealing. *Biomacromolecules*. 2011;12(5):1686–96.
55. Jameson JF, Pacheco MO, Butler JE, Stoppel WL. Estimating Kinetic Rate Parameters for Enzymatic Degradation of Lyophilized Silk Fibroin Sponges. 2021;9(July):1–12.
56. Yan R, Chen Y, Gu Y, Tang C, Huang J, Hu Y, et al. A collagen-coated sponge silk scaffold for functional meniscus regeneration. *J Tissue Eng Regen Med*. 2019 Feb;13(2):156–73.
57. Shang K, Rnjak-Kovacina J, Lin Y, Hayden RS, Tao H, Kaplan DL. Accelerated In Vitro Degradation of Optically Clear Low $\beta\beta\beta$ -Sheet Silk Films by Enzyme-Mediated Pretreatment. *Transl Vis Sci Technol*. 2013;2(3):2.
58. Li G, Yin Y, Zhang Y, Wu J, Sun S. Electrospun regenerated silk fibroin is a promising biomaterial for the maintenance of inner ear progenitors in vitro. *J Biomater Appl*. 2022 Feb;36(7):1164–72.
59. Götz A, Senz V, Schmidt W, Huling J, Grabow N, Illner S. General image fiber tool: A concept for automated evaluation of fiber diameters in SEM images. *Meas J Int Meas Confed*. 2021;177(March).
60. Pensalfini M, Meneghello S, Lintas V, Bircher K, Ehret AE, Mazza E. The suture retention test, revisited and revised. *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater*. 2018;77(August 2017):711–7.
61. Valsecchi E, Biagiotti M, Alessandrino A, Gastaldi D, Vena P, Freddi G. Silk Vascular Grafts with Optimized Mechanical Properties for the Repair and Regeneration of Small Caliber Blood Vessels. *Materials (Basel)*. 2022;15(10):1–18.
62. Laukkarinen J, Nordback I, Mikkonen J, Kärkkäinen P, Sand J. A novel biodegradable biliary stent in the endoscopic treatment of cystic-duct leakage after cholecystectomy. *Gastrointest Endosc*. 2007;65(7):1063–8.
63. König G, McAllister TN, Dusserre N, Garrido SA, Iyican C, Marini A, et al. Mechanical properties of completely autologous human tissue engineered blood vessels compared to human saphenous vein and mammary artery. *Biomaterials*. 2009;30(8):1542–50.
64. Pitt HA, Nakeeb A. Chapter 8 - Bile secretion and pathophysiology of biliary tract obstruction [Internet]. Sixth Edit. Vols. 1–2, Blumgart's Surgery of the Liver, Biliary Tract and Pancreas: Sixth Edition. Elsevier Inc.; 2017. 123-132.e1 p. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-34062-5.00008-X>
65. Abdallah E, Ellatif MA, El Awady S, Magdy A, Youssef M, Thabet W, et al. Is LigaSure a safe cystic duct sealer? An ex vivo study. *Asian J Surg [Internet]*. 2015;38(4):187–90. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.asjsur.2015.03.012>
66. Vanags I, Petersons A, Ose V, Ozolanta I, Kasyanov V, Laizans J, et al. Biomechanical properties of oesophagus wall under loading. *J Biomech*. 2003;36(9):1387–90.
67. Chytrosz P, Golda-Cepa M, Włodarczyk J, Kuzdzal J, El Fray M, Kotarba A. Characterization of Partially Covered Self-Expandable Metallic Stents for Esophageal Cancer Treatment: In Vivo Degradation. *ACS Biomater Sci Eng*. 2021;7(4):1403–13.
68. Hassan K, Kim SH, Park I, Lee SH, Kim SH, Jung Y, et al. Small diameter double layer tubular scaffolds

- using highly elastic PLCL copolymer for vascular tissue engineering. *Macromol Res.* 2011;19(2):122–9.
69. Qian Y, Zheng Y, Jin J, Wu X, Xu K, Dai M, et al. Immunoregulation in Diabetic Wound Repair with a Photoenhanced Glycyrrhizic Acid Hydrogel Scaffold. *Adv Mater.* 2022;34(29):1–15.
 70. Wang F, Guo C, Yang Q, Li C, Zhao P, Xia Q, et al. Protein composites from silkworm cocoons as versatile biomaterials. *Acta Biomater* [Internet]. 2021;121:180–92. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2020.11.037>
 71. Servoli E, Maniglio D, Motta A, Predazzer R, Migliaresi C. Surface properties of silk fibroin films and their interaction with fibroblasts. *Macromol Biosci.* 2005;5(12):1175–83.